

Quantum Wind Rose (Quantum Entanglement)

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Abstract

It shows how the use of probabilities has been something provisional that reflects a lack of knowledge about the values of certain parameters that determine the individual behavior of the particles. The violation of Bell's inequality can be attributed to the conjunction of a predictive completeness which can be understood as an interference, the cause of this interference may be the origin of light diffraction or effects such as double-slit experiment.

Keywords: Quantum entanglement; Spooky action; EPR; Bell's theorem; Light diffraction; Double-slit experiment.

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Introduction

From the point of view of a physics with no hidden variables (Superconducting Field Theory, 2024) [1] it only needs extra dimensions in one case, **Quantum Entanglement or Spooky Action at distance**.

This image taken from a real-time Quantum Entanglement image (Real-Time Imaging of Quantum Entanglement, 2013) [2] shows the polarization pattern and the spatial distribution of a photons group.

Fig. 1: Polarized photons impacts [2]

The **Einstein–Podolsky–Rosen (EPR)** paradox is a thought experiment proposed by physicists Albert Einstein, Boris Podolsky and Nathan Rosen which argues that the description of physical reality provided by quantum mechanics is incomplete. In a 1935 paper titled "Can Quantum-Mechanical Description of Physical Reality be Considered Complete?" [3], they argued for the existence of "elements of reality" that were not part of quantum theory, and speculated that it should be possible to construct a theory containing these hidden variables.

Bell's theorem [4] is a term encompassing a number of closely related results in physics, all of which determine that quantum mechanics is incompatible with local hidden-variable theories.

In the **Copenhagen interpretation**, the result of a spin measurement on one of the particles is a collapse (of wave function) into a state in which each particle has a definite spin (either up or down) along the axis of measurement. The outcome is taken to be random, with each possibility having a probability of 50%. However, if both spins are measured along the same axis, they are found to be anti-correlated. This means that the random outcome of the measurement made on one particle seems to have been transmitted to the other, so that it can make the "right choice" when it too is measured.

In Quantum Entanglement as well as in the **Copenhagen interpretation**, every state has a probability associated with it, and the average result may be predicted using a variety of metrics. Although it is unforeseeable in and of itself, the chance that a single measurement will be up or down depends on these probabilities.

So, is quantum mechanics consistent with Bell's inequality?

1. Probabilities approach

1.1 Calculations

We can distinguish 5 probability zones with a **Compass Rose** shape, using locations **North(N)**, **South(S)**, **East(E)**, **West(W)** and **Center(C)**; the sizes that will occupy approximately each delimited region inside the circle, will be as follows:

- North(N) and South(S): $16'6\% + 16'6\% = 33\%$
- East(E) and West(W): $25\% + 25\% = 50\%$
- Center (C): $8'3\%$

This image consists of 2 detectors (A and B) for 2 specific polarizations.

Quantum Compass Rose

Fig. 2: Impact zones distribution

So, having launched a photon and reached a zone, what is the probability that it belongs to polarization **A or B**? **Simplifying** is close to:

- (C) $P(A)$ or $P(B) = 0\%$
- (N,S) $P(A) = 0\%$
- (N,S) $P(B) = 100\%$
- * (E,W) $P(A) \approx 62'5\%$
- * (E,W) $P(B) \approx 37'5\%$

There is no a regular distribution, because of a collapse probability of the wave function between the zones ***(E,W) P(A) = 62'5%** and ***(E,W) P(B) = 37'5%**, having other locations a probability completely differentiated for each detector.

Fig. 3: Overlapping Wave Function Collapse (OWFC)

Apparently, for these polarizations we should have the same probability in the East-West axis (an excess of impacts in detector A) as in the North-South (only impacts in B). For a basic explanation we settle for this calculation that shows how quantum mechanics is consistent with Bell's inequality.

There are probability calculations more accurate using the size of the reception area or the number of photons emitted. We'll try to make another estimation with the following data (always approximate), using Bayes' theorem:

1. Let's imagine that the following impacts have occurred, **after launching 2000 photons, 1000 to each detector.**

Fig. 4: Probabilistic approach

Having launched a photon and having reached zone W, what is the probability that it is detector A?

Bayes' theorem:

$$P(A|W) = (P(W|A) \times P(A)) / P(W)$$

- Having reached detector A, the probability of hitting W would be $P(W|A) = 0.5$
- The probability of reaching detector A would be $P(A) = 0.5$
- The probability of reaching an area W would be $P(W) = 2.000 / (500 + 300) = 0.4$

$$P(A|W) = (0.5 \times 0.5) / 0.4 = 0.625$$

2. With these zones defined, new calculations can be applied with more polarizations, and we can get closer to Bell's experiments with three different polarizations. **The probability of the areas may differ from how we define these areas, although the basis of this document is the study of quantum entanglement.**

Fig. 5: Violation of Bell's Inequality by Quantum Mechanics

1.2 Geometry

In quantum physics, the scattering amplitude is the probability amplitude of the outgoing spherical wave relative to the incoming plane wave in a stationary-state scattering process; this phenomenon occurs in refraction, but we see that it may also be taking place in some process at the quantum vacuum in a **subatomic scale**.

Despite its wave function, photons behave like if they could reach points with greater probability, as if such wave were influenced by a vacuum formed by some type of twistor that can diffract them with greater probability in certain positions; again compatible with the QDS (Quantum Decimal Spinor), a supersymmetry model conformed by 5 +5 faces structures trying to expand on each axis of space (Superconducting Field Theory, 2024) [1]. Although it was described with a circular internal scattering structure to fit physical systems, how it works at the subatomic level is unknown.

2 polarized prisms; 5 + 5 faces

Fig. 6: Quantum Decimal Spinor (QDS)

2. Probabilities check

2.1 Entanglement

A proposal could be to conform bits using **200 photons for each bit**; thus, we can increase its probability of success (a definition of 200 photons per bit would increase the probability in the interpretation of the communication), always showing the impacts accompanied by their probability. For now, it wouldn't be necessary to automate the whole process, in a first phase, we could write each calculated bit in an Excel file so we can verify the results.

It can be conformed a small image, for example, 15 x 15 or smaller, where each individual cell could be made up of one bit (1 or 0, black or white), trying to make **distance changes between receivers** to ensure the most real spooky communication possible. These data are a first example, it is possible that an image could be obtained with fewer photons per bit; this could put an end to the doubts about quantum entanglement and its application in communications, I guess...

Remember you can **renormalize** until get your expected values.

Fig. 7: Who said spooky!

2.2 Bell polarizations

Personally, I am not sure if Bell's calculations with 3 types of polarization are sufficient, maybe experiments with higher polarizations can indicate a little better how vacuum scattering affects light.

Fig. 8: Scattering due to polarization

3. Conclusions

The vacuum scattering effect can help us understand behaviors such as light diffraction [5] or the double-slit effect. Light behaves in a complex way; it is mostly assumed that photons follow a straight line, although this depends on their bandwidth. A clear example are the shadows derived from sunlight, where the shadow is not totally dark but lighter (also taking into account that light is reflected from other surfaces), therefore, there are photons that reach areas without following the straight line. As an example, in **the double slit experiment** [6] the main parameter that manages to modify the resulting wave pattern is the bandwidth of the original light, and it seems that the smaller the bandwidth, the lower the photon's ability to scatter; this

scattering effect may be due, therefore, to the effect of the vacuum scattering the photons in different points in the form of the indicated wind rose, where each zone has a greater or lesser probability of impact, varying the probabilities the farther we move away from the center and depending mainly on its frequency.

Fig. 9: Diffraction pattern of light

Quantum Entanglement has been studied for more than 80 years, while telecommunications have advanced at a breakneck speed (as well as other applications). Quantum Telecommunications are applications with many commercial outlets, for example, supplying telecommunications in hard-to-reach areas, so it's strange to see that they do not advance and put physics on the ropes.

Are the probabilities being compared correctly? Why is there nothing better in production to capture Alice and Bob?

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